

MORAL LESSONS FROM THE BIBLICAL ACCOUNT OF JOSEPH (GEN. 37 -42) AND THEIR USEFULNESS IN THE DAILY LIFE OF STUDENTS OF ALVAN IKOKU FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION, OWERRI

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Abstract

The study examined the moral lessons from the biblical account of Joseph and the daily life of the students of Alvan Ikoku Federal University Education, Owerri. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Sample size of 300 students was drawn from a population of regular Christian students using purposive-accidental sampling techniques. A researcher developed rating scale titled: Biblical Joseph's Life Story Moral Lessons Rating Scale (BJLSMLRS) was used for data collection. It was validated by 5 experts. It has two clusters: A and B with internal consistency reliability coefficients of 0.86 and 0.88 respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the z-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 levels of significance. Results showed that while the extent of students' awareness of the moral lessons from the biblical account of Joseph is significantly above the expected average, the extent to which they are determined to uphold them in their daily life is significantly below the expected average level. Owing to the findings and their implications, the following recommendations were made: the family needs to put more effort in strengthening these moral lessons/values in the life of the children; the teachers/lecturers who teach and relate with the students should be the epitome of Joseph's account so that the students can easily emulate them; the religious organizations both within and outside the school should put more effort in emphasizing these moral lessons/values so that they can be instilled in students; and the school should ensure that these moral lessons/values like honesty, integrity, responsibility, respect, fleeing from all forms of sexual immorality and wickedness are considered in developing policies and encouraging workers, especially those who are Christians, to show them in their dealings with students.

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Introduction

One of the major problems of many present youths is the inability to learn from life experiences of others. The Holy Scripture contains some individual life experiences that should help us live better in this world, as pilgrims. Life experiences that should encourage us to fear the Lord and keep His commandments (Proverb 12: 13) are abound in the Bible. Experience is a hard teacher because it goes lest first before the lesson (Vernon, as cited in Deepak, 2020). Moral lessons are usually derived from the life experiences of the fathers of faith in the scripture, which help us to grow as Christians. Moral lessons from the experiences of others are really helpful in life. Moral lessons have been defined in various ways. Fiveable Inc. (2025) views it as a feeling or principle conveyed through a story or narrative that imparts ethical guidance or insights into right and wrong behavior. These lessons are often central to a piece's themes, allowing readers to reflect on their own values and choices in relation to the characters' experiences. The lexicon also sees it as a message about right and wrong behaviour and teachings that promote ethical conduct (Reverse Dictionary, 2025).

Today, it appears that only a few Christian youths have a great value for God's word on the life experiences of the fathers of faith in the Scriptures who are no more but their legacies live. Belinda (2020) asserts that she learns either not to speak a certain way or even make certain decisions based on the experiences of people who have done something similar to her. In reasoning if the youth really pay serious attention to God's word as pertaining to daily life and overcoming difficult times. The Christian Women Mirror (CWM, 2025) makes it clearer in this way:

The faith and the truth of the gospel are under constant assault. Some who claim to be preachers and believers have distorted divine principles to accommodate sinful lifestyles, contrary to the teachings of Jude 1:4. Some dismiss serving God as incompatible with the demands of modern living, branding Christianity as outdated in a technologically driven age. Yet Christ's sacrifice and the unchanging word remain the foundation for eternal hope and purpose (Heb. 13:8) (p. 8).

Similarly, the same Christian magazine (CWM, 2025) maintains that education and vocational training, once celebrated as pathways to a brighter future, are being undetermined, especially among young people. A deceptive narrative that this pursuit lacks relevance- a lie from the enemy intended to derail destinies filled with divine potentials.

These strong observations indicate that many present-day youths are not paying attention to God's word. There are several accounts in the Scripture that provide good moral lessons on how youths should behave despite the challenges of life. The life experience of Joseph is filled with moral lessons that enlighten, encourage, and strengthen the youth to live their lives in a way that pleases God despite trials and temptations that might be on their way.

Being an open-minded person, Joseph shared his dream with his family, as recorded in the book of Genesis 37. His integrity made him report to his father the wickedness of his brothers. This means that he understood and hated what evil was. As a young adolescent, Joseph hated wickedness at seventeen years of age. He failed to conceal his brothers' wickedness, which he observed rather than report to their father, who he believed was in a better position to discipline them. As recorded in Gen 37:2, this act is an indicator that he was a person of integrity. Other accounts of his life equally support this claim. Second, in humility, open-heartedness, and with a clear conscience, he shared his dream with his brothers (Gen. 37). On hearing the dreams, his brothers hated him the more.

Second, life is all about contribution. Faiqaazam (2020,p. 1) describes it as follows :

A person's most useful asset is not a heedful of knowledge but a heart full of love and respect, an ear ready to listen, and a hand willing to help others. Your single step cannot change the world, but it can change someone's

world. It shows a sense of responsibility and love for the welfare of the community, then forms a community toward the country and then from the country toward the whole world.

Truly, Joseph was in the habit of contributing to the wellbeing and progress of the people around him. This is evident in various accounts in the Bible. First, when Joseph took food to his brothers at Schechem, where his father sent him for the welfare of his brothers, he did not stop and turned back when he could not see his brothers but on getting information on their whereabouts trekked further from Schechem to Dothan, about 15 miles from Schechem (Israel Bible Team, 2021). When he finally arrived at Potiphar's house, despite being sold as a slave, he worked very hard to earn Potiphar's trust to the extent that he put him in total charge of his house (Weston, 2016). This means that Potiphar gave Joseph complete administrative responsibility over everything he owned.

Furthermore, in his punishment of confinement due to his refusal to accept the evil request of Potiphar's wife, he served to the extent that he did not need to be supervised before he did good work (Dwight, 1982). Though the hand of God was upon him, he was doing his part without minding its cost. Truly, he found favor with God to such an extent that the governor delegated control of all people who are incarcerated to him and appointed him to watch over all their comings and groups (Braun, 2020).

Though Joseph was confined as a punishment, he never allowed it to weigh him down. He neither complained nor murmured; rather, he worked hard to make his fellow people who are incarcerated happy.

And today, if there is anything we need more than ever for our walk to the kingdom, it is a kindly, genuine contribution to our ecclesiast. We need to make our contribution to the service of the truth constantly and humbly. We all have a part to play every day; God is constantly putting opportunities in our way for us to take and use as best as we can. Every day we pass people who are thirsting for the truth. Every day we pass people who are miserable upset, losing faith and hope. And yet for all this, we have fire within us that can be used to tell people that God loves them. We have the opportunity to listen to their problems, offer a shoulder to cry on a friendly smile lost nothing, all it lost is the realization that we want to make a difference every day that we live (Tiding Publishing Company, 2025, p. 6).

Again, he never disappointed Pharaoh when he committed the whole process of farming, harvesting, and storing food to prevent the coming famine. He worked very hard to ensure that he met his expectations. It is clear that he worked for the good of the people in trouble or out of trouble. Nothing stopped him from achieving this goal. Joseph is the remarkable epitome of forgiveness just as Christians are enjoined to forgive as the Lord forgave us (Colossians 3:12). Years after his brothers sold Joseph into slavery, a journey that started from the pit faced with several trials and temptations, he chose to love and forgive his brothers. Indeed, choosing love and forgiveness over hate is extremely challenging (Snuggs, 2024), but Joseph did the right thing. The Bible in Genesis 50: 16-21 puts it this way "Joseph refuses to give in to Potiphar's wife's request of committing adultery with her". According to Kurt (2012), Joseph would sin against God if he gratified his desires. Joseph had a deep relationship with God such that it would grieve Joseph to sin against him. He could not bear to disappoint the God he loved. Joseph's action against Potiphar's wife request to go to bed with her is a clear indication that he really loved God with all his heart, soul, and mind, as seen in Matt 22:37. Joseph recognized that Potiphar's wife's adulterous request was a sin against God and humanity, and as a result, he decided not to be with her, as seen in verse 10 of Gen 39. Furthermore, when Potiphar's wife wanted to force him after her seduction failed, Joseph ran away from her. Surprisingly, this righteous act landed him in prison. However, the favor of God was upon him.

There are many lessons to be learned from Joseph's story. According to Khalil (2025), Joseph's story shows that: God can work with young people, that they obey God's commandments, that God will bring them to light, and that evil can be turned into good. In the same vein, Teis (2014) enumerates some lessons to be learned from

the life of Jacob and Joseph: God knows who you are, God has not forgotten you, God has a plan for your life, God wants you to seek His face, God wants you to be obedient to Him no matter the circumstances, and God will bless you for your obedience. Based on these, God only requires patience despite challenges, obedience, and trust in Him to surmount all obstacles one might experience. Youths need to possess Christian virtues to obtain God's favor in life, as Joseph's story entails. Lives Changed by Christ (LCBC, 2020) maintains that the story of Joseph in the scripture tells us: to always acknowledge the truth, to trust God's plan; and to rely on God. Similarly, it has been pointed out that the spiritual lessons from Joseph's story include the following:

- God's dreams can make others uncomfortable
- Nothing stops God's plans.
- In difficult times, always watch for how God shows up.
- Integrity and obedience (to God's word) beat lies at all times;
- God will test you even if you are called;
- God knows your readiness for leadership.
- God will push you into a leadership purpose.
- People deserve a second chance. (The Faith Space, n.d.).

Next to Jesus, Joseph may be the greatest example of godly character and integrity in the Bible (Andrew Wommack Ministries, 2025, para.3). The Biblical account of Joseph contains sufficient information on how our youths, mostly adolescents, should live their lives. Contrarily, many of our youths in tertiary institutions indulge in many unwholesome practices, such as sorting of failed exams, lying, stealing, sexual immorality, quarreling, unforgiving spirits, disrespectfulness, and being indolent. They see some of these sinful lifestyles as compatible with the present technological age. One thing that surprises one is that many of our youths who indulge in some aforementioned practices are Christians. This is really worrisome, and it lends to portray that many of them are unaware of Joseph's life story or they are aware but have not got the conviction to live like Joseph, being truthful and shunning all forms of sins or wickedness notwithstanding the temporary pains some of them might cause them. Could the claim of the researchers be through and through? It is against this backdrop that the researchers decided to investigate the moral lessons from the Biblical account of Joseph and its usefulness in the daily life of Christian students of Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study

1. To what extent are the Christian students fully aware of the moral lessons from Joseph's Biblical account?
2. To what extent have the Christian students decided to uphold the moral lessons from Joseph's story in their daily lives?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed and tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

1. The extent of students' awareness of the moral lesson from the biblical account of Joseph is not significantly different from the expected average level.
2. The extent to which Christian students have decided to uphold the moral lessons from the Joseph story in their daily lives is not significantly different from the expected average level.

Method

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design.

The study population comprised all regular Christian students of Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education. The PACS technique was used to draw a sample size of 300 students. The researchers developed a rating scale

titled: Joseph Life Story Moral Lesson Rating Scale (JLSMLRS) for data collection. It consisted of two clusters: clusters A and cluster B. Clusters A and B focused on the level of awareness of students of the moral lessons from Joseph’s life story and the level of their decision to act like Joseph if faced with similar challenges. Both clusters are structured on a four-point scale of: High Extent (HE) (4-Point); Moderate Extent (ME) (3-point); Low Extent (LE) (2-point); and No Extent (NE) (1-point). Each of the two clusters contains 17 items. The instrument was validated by three experts in the field of Educational Measurement and Evaluation and two experts in the field of Christian Religious Studies. Cronbach’s alpha was used to establish the reliability coefficient of the internal consistency of clusters A and B of the instrument at 0.86 and 0.88, respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while z-test statistics were used to test the hypotheses at a p-value of 0.05. Both items and respondents were used as data analysis units. Item mean was used to determine the level of students’ awareness of each of the 17 moral lessons from Joseph’s life story and the extent to which they have decided to uphold them in their daily life despite the challenges they may face. The expected average level is the product of the number of items in each cluster and the average of the four-point scale (2.5) (that is $17 \times 2.5 = 42.50$). The cluster/observed mean of the extent of students’ awareness decision is compared with the expected mean.

Results

Table 1: The extent to which Christian students are fully aware of the moral lessons from the biblical account of Joseph

S/N	Item Statements	X	S	Dec.
1	Open-heartedness to nuclear family members	2.22	0.58	LE
2	Love everyone around us	2.79	0.70	ME
3	Murmur not despite the offense	1.39	0.49	NE
4	Recognize sin and avoid living in it	2.75	0.71	ME
5	Flee from all forms of sexual immorality	2.22	0.58	LE
6	Value our relationship with God more than anything else	2.22	0.58	LE
7	Contribute to the progress and well-being of others	2.46	0.50	LE
8	Reporting crimes to the appropriate authorities	2.46	0.50	LE
9	Know that God will test us even if we are not called	2.40	0.49	LE
10	Know that God’s dream for you can make others uncomfortable	2.90	0.80	ME
11	Know that in difficult times, one needs to be observant when God shows up.	3.01	0.78	ME
12	Know that nothing stops God’s plan if you obey him	2.22	0.58	LE
13	Forgive and let go of offences	3.01	0.78	ME
14	Trusting God’s plan for us	3.01	0.78	ME
15	Know that God knows your readiness for leadership.	3.13	0.78	ME
16	Always acknowledge the truth	3.13	0.78	ME
17	Refuse to be where we could easily be lured into sin.	2.46	0.50	LE
	Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation	43.83	2.11	AEAL

AEAL= Above Expected Average Level

Table 1 shows the mean, standard deviation, and decision taken for the items. It shows that the item with serial number 3 has a mean value of approximately 1, which indicates no extent, whereas that of 1, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 12, and 17 have a mean value of approximately 2 (i.e., to the nearest whole), each of which indicates low extent.

The items with serial numbers 2, 4, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, and 16 have a mean value of approximately 3 (i.e., to the nearest whole number, which indicates a moderate extent). The cluster/observed mean and standard deviation are 3.83 and 2.11, respectively, which are above the expected average level.

Table 4: Summary of the z-test results of Hypothesis One

Category of the Mean	X	S	z-cal.	SL	z-tab.	Decision
Cluster mean	43.83	2.11	10.90	0.05	1.96	H ₀₁ rejected
Expected	42.50					

Table 4 shows that z-calculated (10.90) is greater than z-tabulated at 0.05 significance levels (1.96). The null hypothesis is rejected because the z-calculated is greater than the z-tabulated at a significance level of 0.05. This means that the students’ cluster/observed mean is significantly different from the expected average.

Table 3: The extent to which Christian students have decided to uphold the moral lessons from the story of Joseph in their daily lives

S/N	Item statements	X	S	Dec.
1	Open-heartedness to nuclear family members	1.73	0.68	LE
2	Love everyone around us	1.62	0.67	LE
3	Murmur not despite the offense	1.87	0.91	LE
4	Recognize sin and avoid living in it	2.10	1.02	LE
5	Flee from all forms of sexual immorality	1.95	0.85	LE
6	Value our relationship with God more than anything else	1.93	0.83	LE
7	Contribute to the progress and well-being of others	2.35	1.03	LE
8	Reporting crimes to the appropriate authorities	1.35	0.48	NE
9	Prepare for God’s Test when we are called	1.87	0.91	LE
10	Overlook the jealousy of some family members who may not be happy when God has called us	1.87	0.91	LE
11	Preserving and being patient in waiting for God’s help in difficult times instead of giving up	2.30	1.08	LE
12	Live in total obedience to God’s word for His plan to be materialized	1.87	0.91	LE
13	Forgive and let go of offences	1.93	0.83	LE
14	Trusting God’s plan for us	2.99	0.74	ME
15	Know that God knows your readiness for leadership.	2.99	0.74	ME
16	Always acknowledge the truth	2.35	1.03	LE
17	Refuse to be where we could easily be lured into sin.	2.69	0.98	ME
	Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation	35.79	2.36	BEAL

Table 3 shows the respondents’ item mean in the extent to which they are determined to uphold the moral lessons for the story of Joseph in the course of living their life in their own generation. The table shows items with serial numbers: 8 has mean value of approximately 1 (i.e., to the nearest whole number), which indicates no extent. All the other items have mean value of approximately 2, indicating a low extent, while the cluster/observed mean is 35.79, which is below the expected average of 42.50 (i.e. $2.5 \times 17 = 42.50$)

Table 4: Summary of the z-test results of Hypothesis Two

Category of the Mean	X	S	z-cal.	SL	z-tab.	Decision
Cluster mean	35.79	2.36	49.16	0.05	1.96	H ₀₂ rejected
Expected	42.50					

Table 4 shows that z-calculated (49.16) is greater than z-tabulated at 0.05 significance levels (1.96). The null hypothesis is rejected because the z-calculated value is greater than the z-tabulated value at 0.05 significance levels. This means that the students' cluster/observed mean is significantly different from the expected average.

Discussion of the Results

The study found that the level of students' awareness of the moral lessons from Joseph's life story is significantly above the expected average. This is very good as it shows that these students have come to learn moral values that will enable them to overcome some of life challenges that are more likely to come their way as they grow through their religious organizations, moral instructions during secondary schools, through Christian Religious Studies (CRS) in secondary schools or through their elders/parents. However, some specific moral lessons need to be emphasized so that they will be fully aware of them. They include the following: ability not to murmur over offences; fleeing from all forms of sexual immoralities; valuing our relationship with God more than anything else; and contributing to the progress and well-being of others where the findings indicate either no extent or low extent.

The findings also show that the extent to which the respondents were determined to upload or apply the identified moral lessons in their lives is significantly below the expected average. This is not healthy for the students themselves, their families, the school community, and the larger society. Moral values, such as honesty, integrity, perseverance, and self-discipline, are the building blocks of good character and the ability to think critically, consider different perspectives, and make fair and just decisions (Satyamevjayate International School, 2025). Owing to the findings, it seems that the stakeholders in whose hands it lies to instill these moral values in students need to put more effort in some areas such as: being prepared for God's test when we are called; overlooking the jealousy of some family members who may not be happy when God has called us; being prepared in waiting (i.e., patient) for God's intervention when we are in trouble; forgiving all offences, listening to God's plan, and many other areas the findings show low extent. It is obvious that the students have not come to a point of upholding all these moral lessons to a high extent, and unless this is achieved, the desired expectation of students behaving like Joseph when confronted with similar life situations may not be achieved.

Conclusion

This study examined the moral lessons in Joseph's story and ascertained the level to which students are aware of the moral lessons and the extent to which they are determined to upload them in their lives. These findings are critical and need to be explored and harnessed by all stakeholders for the benefit of our students and society. It will be a great blessing to our society and nation when most people emulate Joseph in the Bible.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and their implications, we recommend the following.

- I. The family needs to put more effort into strengthening these moral lessons/values in the children's lives.

- II. The teachers/lecturers who teach and relate to the students should be the epitome of Joseph's account so that the students can easily emulate them.
- III. Religious organizations both within and outside the school should put more effort into emphasizing these moral lessons/values so that they can be instilled in students.
- IV. The school should ensure that these moral lessons/values, such as honesty, integrity, responsibility, respect, fleeing from all forms of sexual immorality, and shunning wickedness, are considered in the development of its policies and encourage its workers, especially Christians, to show them in their dealings with students.

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Appendix I

Instrument used for data collection

Joseph's Life Story Moral Lessons Rating Scale

Instruction: Please read carefully and choose the option that best describes your opinion for each item.

Note: High Extent (HE) (4 points); Moderate Extent (ME) (3 points); Low Extent (LE) (2 points); and No Extent (NE) (1 point)

Cluster A

The Extent Christian Students Are Fully Aware of Moral Lessons from the Biblical Account of Joseph

To what extent are Christian students fully aware of the moral lessons from Joseph's biblical account?

S/N	Item statements: According to Joseph's Story, we have to exhibit the following:	HE	ME	LE	NE
1	Open-heartedness to nuclear family members				
2	Love everyone around us				
3	Murmur not despite the offense				
4	Recognize sin and avoid living in it				
5	Flee from all forms of sexual immorality				
6	Value our relationship with God more than anything else				
7	Contribute to the progress and well-being of others				
8	Reporting crimes to the appropriate authorities				
9	Know that God will test us even if we are not called				
10	Know that God's dream for you can make others uncomfortable				
11	Know that in difficult times, one needs to be observant when God shows up.				
12	Know that nothing stops God's plan if you obey him				
13	Forgive and let go of offences				
14	Trusting God's plan for us				
15	Know that God knows your readiness for leadership.				
16	Always acknowledge the truth				

17	Refuse to be where we could easily be lured into sin.				
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Cluster B

The Extent of Christian Students’ Decision to Uphold the Moral Lessons from Joseph Story in their Daily Life

To what extent do Christian students resolve to uphold the moral lessons from Joseph’s story in their daily lives?

S/N	Item Statements	HE	ME	LE	NE
1	Open-heartedness to nuclear family members				
2	Love everyone around us				
3	Murmur not despite the offense				
4	Recognize sin and avoid living in it				
5	Flee from all forms of sexual immorality				
6	Value our relationship with God more than anything else				
7	Contribute to the progress and well-being of others				
8	Reporting crimes to the appropriate authorities				
9	Prepare for God’s Test when we are called				
10	Overlook the jealousy of some family members who may not be happy when God has called us				
11	Preserving and being patient in waiting for God’s help in difficult times instead of giving up				
12	Live in total obedience to God’s word for His plan to materialize				
13	Forgive and let go of offences				
14	Trusting God’s plan for us				
15	Know that God knows your readiness for leadership.				
16	Always acknowledge the truth				
17	Refuse to be where we could easily be lured into sin.				

Results of Data Analysis Concerning Question 1

Item mean

S/N	Item Statements	4	3	2	1	X	S	Dec.-
1	Open-heartedness to nuclear family members	-	90	186	24	2.22	0.58	LE
2	Love everyone around us	50	138	162	-	2.79	0.70	ME
3	Murmur not despite the offense	-	-	118	182	1.39	0.49	NE
4	Recognize sin and avoid living in it	48	128	124	-	2.75	0.71	ME
5	Flee from all forms of sexual immorality	-	90	186	24	2.22	0.58	LE
6	Value our relationship with God more than anything else	-	90	186	24	2.22	0.58	LE
7	Contribute to the progress and well-being of others	-	138	162	-	2.46	0.50	LE

8	Reporting crimes to the appropriate authorities	-	138	162	-	2.46	0.50	LE
9	Know that God will test us even if we are not called	-	119	181	-	2.40	0.49	LE
10	Know that God's dream for you can make others uncomfortable	82	106	112	-	2.90	0.80	ME
11	Know that in difficult times, one needs to be observant when God shows up.	92	118	90	-	3.01	0.78	ME
12	Know that nothing stops God's plan if you obey him	-	90	186	24	2.22	0.58	LE
13	Forgive and let go of offences	92	118	90	-	3.01	0.78	ME
14	Trusting God's plan for us	92	118	90	-	3.01	0.78	ME
15	Know that God knows your readiness for leadership.	112	115	73	-	3.13	0.78	ME
16	Always acknowledge the truth	112	115	73	-	3.13	0.78	ME
17	Refuse to be where we could easily be lured into sin.	-	138	162	-	2.46	0.50	LE
	Cluster mean and Standard Deviation					43.83	2.11	AEAL

Cluster/Observed Mean and Standard Deviation Concerning Question 1

S/N	X	F
1	48	15
2	47	20
3	46	33
4	45	43
5	44	61
6	43	46
7	42	37
8	41	25
9	40	20

$X = 43.83$ $S = 2.107$

Z-test of Hypothesis One

$X_c = \text{cluster/observed mean} = 43.83$

$S_c = \text{cluster/observed standard deviation} = 2.11$

$X_E = \text{expected mean} = 2.5 \times 17 = 42.50$

$N = 300$

$Z =$

$=$

$=$

$=$

$= 10.90$

Results of Data Analysis Concerning Question 2

Item mean

S/N	Item Statements	HE (2)	ME (3)	LE (2)	NE (1)	X	S	Dec.
1	Open-heartedness to nuclear family members	-	40	138	122	1.73	0.68	LE
2	Love everyone around us	-	32	123	145	1.62	0.67	LE
3	Murmur not despite the offense	20	48	106	126	1.87	0.91	LE
4	Recognize sin and avoid living in it	38	58	99	105	2.10	1.02	LE
5	Flee from all forms of sexual immorality	20	42	142	96	1.95	0.85	LE
6	Value our relationship with God more than anything else	15	48	138	99	1.93	0.83	LE
7	Contribute to the progress and well-being of others	50	78	99	13	2.35	1.03	LE
8	Reporting crimes to the appropriate authorities	-	-	106	194	1.35	0.48	NE
9	Prepare for God’s Test when we are called	20	48	156	136	1.87	0.91	LE
10	Overlook the jealousy of some family members who may not be happy when God has called us	20	48	156	136	1.87	0.91	LE
11	Preserving and being patient in waiting for God’s help in difficult times instead of giving up	38	58	99	85	2.30	1.08	LE
12	Live in total obedience to God’s word for His plan to materialize	20	48	156	136	1.87	0.91	LE
13	Forgive and let go of offences	15	48	138	99	1.93	0.83	LE
14	Trusting God’s plan for us	80	138	82	-	2.99	0.74	ME
15	Know that God knows your readiness for leadership.	80	138	82	-	2.99	0.74	ME
16	Always acknowledge the truth	50	138	99	73	2.35	1.03	LE
17	Refuse to be where we could easily be lured into sin.	78	86	102	34	2.69	0.98	ME
18	Cluster mean and Standard Deviation					35.79	2.36	BEAL

Cluster/Observed Mean and Standard Deviation Concerning Question 2

S/N	X	F
1	41	7
2	40	16
3	39	20
4	38	30
5	37	38
6	36	51
7	35	42
8	34	37

8	33	32
10	32	27

35.79, 2.36

Z-test of Hypothesis Two

$X_c = \text{cluster/observed mean} = 35.79$

$S_c = \text{cluster/observed standard deviation} = 2.36$

$XE = \text{expected mean} = 2.5 \times 17 = 42.50$

$N = 300$

$Z =$

$=$

$=$

$=$

$= 49.1638$

$= 49.16$

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